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Catalyst-Free Mass Polymerization and Characterization of Bio-Polyhydroxyurethanes Based on Resorcinol Bis(Cyclocarbonate)

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we report the synthesis and characterization of non-isocyanate polyhydroxyurethanes (PHUs) derived from resorcinol bis(cyclocarbonate) (RCC). The PHUs were obtained through polyaddition between RCC and two aliphatic diamines, namely isophoronediamine and Priamine 1075 (a commercial vegetal based diamine), selected due their eco-friendliness, under mild conditions, without the use of toxic isocyanates and catalysts. The resulting materials were characterized by FTIR, NMR spectroscopy, GPC, DSC, and TGA to evaluate their chemical structure, molecular weight distribution, and thermal properties. Then, the processability of the synthesized PHUs was assessed and further functional characterizations, such as mechanical and viscoelastic properties, swelling and water contact angle tests, were performed. Finally, the RCC based PHUs were tested as potential adhesives for aluminium, polymer composite, and wood substrates. All the results highlight that RCC based PHUs are promising sustainable alternatives to fossil-based polyurethanes.

1 | Introduction

The design and synthesis of new materials from renewable resources to replace traditional materials obtained from fossil resources is currently one of the most challenging fields of research. Indeed, the deep dependence on fossil resources represents a primary issue involving economic and environmental sectors [1]. In the field of polymers, various strategies are carried out to improve the sustainability of the employed materials, such as their recycling [2–6], the exploitation of biomasses [7–10] or sustainable solvents [11–14].

In this context, one of the most followed approaches is based on the synthesis of new tailored monomers, used for the real-

ization of biobased polymers [15, 16]. The definition of biobased polymers takes into account the biobased amount: a polymer containing at least 20% of biomass phase is considered partly biobased [17].

Since their high property tunability, polyurethanes are amongst the most used polymers in several industrial sectors, such as automotive, insulation, coatings, packaging, textiles and electronics [18]. Indeed, polyurethanes are widely exploited as elastomers, thermosets, thermoplastics and foams with tunable rigidity. Polyurethanes are also added to nanofillers or nanofibers to obtain nanocomposites with enhanced characteristics, such as mechanical or electrical properties [19, 20].

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However, their environmental sustainability is often debated, since they are traditionally obtained by the reaction between fossil based polyols and isocyanates. During the years, researchers moved their attention toward biobased alternatives, and either biobased polyols [21–23] and biobased polyisocyanates [24, 25] have been produced, opening the doors to the synthesis of fully biobased polyurethanes [26, 27].

Nevertheless, isocyanates are harmful and their synthesis requires the use of highly environmental impacting processes. To replace isocyanate-based polyurethanes, recently non-isocyanate polyurethanes synthesis is emerging as a trending topic in the field of polyurethanes industry [28–31].

Among non-isocyanate polyurethane synthesis, a highly promising strategy involves the aminolysis of biobased cyclocarbonates [32], which leads to the formation of hydroxyurethane monomers and, subsequently, through a step-growth polyaddition mechanism, polyhydroxyurethanes (PHUs) [33–35]. A very interesting advantage of using biobased cyclocarbonates lies in the exploiting of CO₂ as a reaction reagent with diols or epoxies to obtain them [36–39]. Diols can also react with urea or carbonates to obtain cyclocarbonates [40–45].

The reaction between cyclocarbonates and diamine to obtain PHUs usually involves catalysts, such as triazabicyclodecene [46] and thiourea [47]. In order to optimize green synthesis, an important goal consists of the development of procedures which prevent the use of toxic solvents or catalysts [48, 49].

In this work, resorcinol bis(cyclocarbonate) (RCC), obtained from lignin as renewable source, was selected as a monomer for the synthesis of PHUs. In details, RCC was reacted in mass with two different diamines, i.e. IPD, a commercial isophoronediamine, also available from biobased source under the commercial name Vestamin IPD, produced by Evonik, and Priamine 1075, a commercial vegetable oil based diamine. PHUs were thermally and spectroscopically analyzed and were processed and tested as compression moulded films. Then, obtained PHUs were tested as adhesive matrices for metal and composite bars, due to their mechanical performances. With this approach, we paved the way for the realization of fully bio-based PHUs and the showed results revealed the interesting potential of RCC based PHUs in their application as bio-based eco-friendly adhesive layers.

2 | Experimental Section

2.1 | Materials

3-Aminomethyl-3,5,5-trimethylcyclohexylamine (isophoronediamine, IPD), mixture of stereoisomers, tetrahydrofuran (THF, 99.9%) and lithium bromide (LiBr) were provided by Sigma Aldrich (Milan, IT). Priamine 1075 was kindly supplied by Croda Italiana S.p.A. (Mortara Italy). Resorcinol bis(cyclocarbonate) (RCC) was kindly provided by Specific Polymers (Castries, FR). All chemicals were used as received, without further purification.

A carbon fiber-reinforced cured tetraglycidyl diaminodiphenylmethane-based thermosetting polymer (CFRP)

was provided by Alenia Aermacchi (Pomigliano d'Arco, Italy). Aluminum sheets were kindly supplied by Goppion (Milan, Italy). Deal sheets were obtained by Bricocenter (Naples, Italy).

2.2 | PHUs Synthesis

All the syntheses were conducted in bulk at 120°C for 2 h under nitrogen flow and under mechanical stirring, without using catalysts and solvents. The molar ratio between the cyclocarbonates and the total amount of diamines was 1:1 in all cases. To evaluate the effect of the diamines on the properties of PHUs, different diamine mixtures were investigated, as shown in Table 1. RCC was reacted with either Priamine or IPD (samples coded RP and RI, respectively) and then both amines were employed for further syntheses, investigating the Priamine/IPD molar ratios 3:1, 1:1, and 1:3 (codes RP75I25, RP50I50RP, and RP25I75, respectively).

After the synthesis, the polymers were washed with ethanol and methanol to remove the unreacted monomers. After washing, the reaction yield of the performed synthesis was calculated by considering the weight ratio between the amount of the realized polymers and the employed monomers.

2.3 | Characterization

The purified PHU samples were characterized by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR), gel permeation chromatography (GPC), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA).

FTIR analysis was performed with a PerkinElmer Spectrum One FTIR spectrometer equipped with an ATR module, using a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and 32 scan collections.

NMR analysis was performed by means of a Bruker Avance III 600 spectrometer, equipped with a 5-mm CPTCI CryoProbe, using deuterated DMSO as solvent.

GPC analyses were performed in THF (Romil Ltd. Cambridge, UK) at 35°C, with a flow rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹ and a runtime of 45 min, by means of a Malvern-Viscotek GPC MAX/TDA 305 triple detector array (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., Malvern, UK). The column set was composed of a precolumn and two Phenogel (Phenomenex, USA) columns, with exclusion limits of 10⁶ and 10³ Da, respectively. The samples were dissolved in THF (≈5–6.5 mg mL⁻¹) with the addition of 10 mM of LiBr and filtered through a 0.22 μm PTFE membrane filter before injection (100 μL). The chosen evaluation method was universal calibration, based on narrow polystyrene standards, dissolved and injected as samples, with a molecular weight ranging from 1290 MDa to 1700 kDa. All measurements were performed in duplicate.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis was performed on the synthesized PHU samples in the range from -70°C to 200 at 10°C min⁻¹ under nitrogen flow using a DSC-Q1000 from TA Instruments (New Castle, DE, USA).

TABLE 1 | Compositions of the synthesized PHUs, reaction yields and molecular weights measured by GPC.

Code	RCC (mol)	Priamine 1075 (mol)	IPD (mol)	Yield (%)	Mn (kDa)	Mw (kDa)	Polidispersity index (PDI)
RP	1.00	1.00	—	95.4	82.1	91.7	1.11
RP75I25	1.00	0.75	0.25	94.6	49.3	71.1	1.44
RP50I50	1.00	0.50	0.50	70.0	12.0	16.2	1.35
RP25I75	1.00	0.25	0.75	35.3	15.9	19.2	1.21
RI	1.00	—	1.00	<1%	—	—	—

TGA was performed by heating the samples from 25°C to 600°C at a rate of 20°C min⁻¹ in oxidative conditions, with a 5 min isothermal step at 100°C to allow the eventual humidity evaporation, using a PerkinElmer Pyris Diamond TG/DTA (Waltham, MA).

To evaluate the mechanical properties and the hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity of PHUs, thin films (≈100 μm thick) were prepared by compression moulding at 150°C using a hot platen press Collin P200 (Collin Lab and Pilot Solutions GmbH, Maitenbeth, Germany).

Tensile tests were performed on dumb-bell specimens (4 mm² cross section, ≈100 μm thickness, 25 mm gauge length) at a cross-head speed of 10 mm min⁻¹ by using a 5564 Instron machine (Pianezza, Italy), according to ASTM D638 test method. Young's modulus (E) and elongation at break (ε_R) were calculated as average values over at least 5 tested samples.

Water contact angle (WCA) was measured through a First Ten Ångströms FTA 1000 instrument (Portsmouth, VA, USA). PHU films were attached on a double-sided tape applied on a microscope glass and a 1 μL distilled water droplet was positioned on the film surface. Each measurement was repeated on six different areas of the sample. The experiments were conducted at room temperature. WCA was geometrically evaluated as the angle formed by the solid surface and the tangent to the droplet.

Rheological characterization of the film-forming PHUs, i.e. RP, RP75I25, and RP50I50, was carried out using a RheoStress 6000 (Thermo Scientific) rotational rheometer equipped with a parallel plate geometry, 20 mm plate diameter and 0.3 mm gap. First, the monomers mixtures were heated from 30°C to 120°C to induce the polymerization (heating rate 0.1°C s⁻¹), and then the temperature was kept constant at 120°C for 2 h. For all the measurements, oscillation tests were performed at 2% ± 2% over a frequency of 1 Hz.

Equilibrium water content (EWC) and gel content (GC) of RP, RP75I25, and RP50I50 were calculated measuring the weight of the samples after immersion in water for 1, 2, and 7 days. EWC and GC were calculated as follows:

$$GC (\%) = 100 * W_{\text{extr},t} / W_{\text{dry},0} \quad (1)$$

$$EWC (\%) = 100 * (W_{\text{wet},t} - W_{\text{dry},0}) / W_{\text{dry},0} \quad (2)$$

where: $W_{\text{extr},t}$ is the dry weight of the sample after soaking in water for $t = 1, 2,$ or 7 days, $W_{\text{dry},0}$ is the weight of the dry sample before water immersion, and $W_{\text{wet},t}$ is the weight of the sample containing absorbed water after immersion in water for $t = 1, 2,$ or 7 days.

Selected PHU formulations were also tested as adhesives for aluminum, CFRP and wood. For this purpose, aluminum, CFRP and wood specimens were prepared for single lap-shear tests. In details, joints of aluminum, epoxy-based CFRP and wood substrates were bonded with the RP and the RP75I25 materials. Aluminum and CFRP plates, 3 mm thick, were cut to obtain samples 100 mm long and 16 mm wide. To improve the wetting of the substrate with the PHU mixture, the plates were mechanically sandblasted. Thin layers (≈100 μm thick) of presynthesized RP and RP75I25 were applied on the end part of one aluminum or CFRP plate, and distributed over an area of 16 x 16 mm². The second aluminum or CFRP plate was then respectively applied and the joint specimens were cured under a hot platen press at 150°C for 5 min applying a low pressure (<5 bar) on the overlapped area of the plates to prevent leakage of the PHU adhesive layers. Single lap shear tests of adhesive were performed according to ASTM D1002 using an Instron 4505 (Pianezza, Italy) equipped with 1 kN loading cell. Three specimens for aluminum and CFRP samples joints prepared with RP and RP75I25 adhesives were tested. Tests were performed at 1.3 mm min⁻¹ crosshead speed at 25°C and 50 RH%.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was carried out by means of a FEI Quanta 200 FEG SEM (Eindhoven, The Netherlands) in low vacuum mode on the samples after lap shear tests. Moreover, surfaces after lap shear tests were also investigated by a Lynx EVO stereomicroscope (Vision Engineering Ltd, Milan, Italy).

To estimate the applicability of the adhesive PHUs with respect to their thermomechanical properties, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) were performed on RP and RP75I25 by the means of a Discovery DMA 850. Samples were heated from -20°C to 70°C, heating rate 5°C min⁻¹, characterized in tensile mode, amplitude 20 μm, frequency 1 Hz.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Study of the Polymerization Reaction

Results show that, depending on the amines used, the reaction yield varies significantly (Table 1). In particular, the yield of the

synthesis significantly decreased by increasing the amount of IPD. For sample RI the yield was very low, below 1%. The amount of recovered material was then not enough to characterize the polymer. This behavior can be associated to the reactivity of some diamines in reactions with cyclic carbonates, which can be noticeably reduced due to steric hindrance around the amine group. When bulky or branched groups are present near the nitrogen, they can make it more difficult for the amine to approach and react with the carbonate ring. For this reason, sterically hindered diamines tend to be less reactive under standard conditions, and may require the use of a solvent, a catalyst or higher temperatures to reach similar reaction progress [50, 51]. Therefore, all the characterizations were performed on RP, RP75I25, RP50I50, and RP25I75.

The reaction between RCC and the selected diamines was monitored by FTIR and NMR spectroscopy. FTIR spectra of PHUs synthesized from RCC and Priamine/IPD mixtures are reported in Figure 1a. By comparison, FTIR spectra of the monomers are also reported. During the reaction, the strongest peak centered at 1785 cm^{-1} , assigned to the cyclic carbonate group, and well evident in the spectrum of RCC, disappears, indicating the consumption of the bis-cyclic dicarbonate [52]. Next, new peaks typical of hydroxyurethane bonding appear in all the PHU samples, at 3312 , 1687 , and 1538 cm^{-1} . Moreover, FTIR analysis highlights the relative content of Priamine and IPD in the analyzed PHUs, as evidenced by the $-\text{CH}$ stretching band in the $2800\text{--}3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. In details, the absorption bands centred at 2921 and 2852 cm^{-1} is band appear sharper in samples RP and RP75I25, and becomes progressively more broadened and convoluted, due to the intensity increase of the absorption band typical of IPD, in RP50I50 and RP25I75. Although the absorption band of IPD centred at 2899 cm^{-1} never becomes more intense than the bands of the Priamine unit, the magnified view in Figure 1a clearly reflects the variation in composition due to the relative presence of the two diamines used in the formulations. NMR proton spectra were recorded on samples RP, RP75I25, RP50I50, and RP25I75 dissolved in DMSO- d_6 , the spectra are reported in Figure 1b. As a first result, NMR spectra confirm the reaction of the cyclic carbonate with the formation of hydroxyurethane bonds. In fact, the characteristic signals of the cyclic carbonate, found at about 4.24, 4.5, and 5 ppm [52], are almost completely absent. At the same time, the signals attributed to the newly formed $\text{CH}_2\text{--OH}$, CH--OH , and CH--O-- (see structures reported in Figure 1b) are evidenced by the strong, unresolved band located between 3.7 and 4.1 ppm and by the peak at 4.8 ppm [53]. Furthermore, the $\text{CH}_2\text{--NH--}$ group of reacted Priamine units can be identified at 2.95 ppm while the corresponding groups of reacted IPD units can be identified at 2.72 (CH--NH--) and 3.55 ($\text{CH}_2\text{--NH--}$) ppm [53, 54]. The signals observed in these areas in the RP sample, where IPD is absent, were assigned to impurities (3.55 and 2.75 ppm) and to the satellite of the residual DMSO signal (2.67 ppm); Figure S1 reports a magnification of this region for all spectra.

With this in mind, the incorporation of both IPD (I) and Priamine (P) units into the formed polymers is demonstrated by the above mentioned peaks, as well as by the appearance of new signals in the aliphatic CH_n region ($0.5\text{--}1.6\text{ ppm}$) in materials with increasing content of IPD, compared to the RP sample.

A quantitative determination of the two components is hindered by the strong overlapping of their peaks in the upfield region and by the presence of impurities, as discussed above. Nevertheless, by comparing the area of the peak at 2.95, attributed to P, and the peaks at 2.72 and 3.55 ppm, attributed to I, an estimation of the actual P/I ratio can be obtained. While in the RP75I25 PHU sample the P/I ratio is close to the nominal value of 3/1, in the RP50I50 and RP25I75 samples this ratio is lower than expected ($\approx 1/0.7$ instead of 1/1, $\approx 1/1.5$ instead of 1/3, respectively). This finding indicates a lower reactivity of IPD in the polymerization conditions tested and can be correlated to the lower polymerization yield obtained with increasing the IPD content.

GPC analysis confirmed the extent of the significant effect of the IPD/Priamine ratio on the polymerization of resorcinol based PHU. Indeed, as shown in Table 1, the RP sample, obtained from the reaction of RCC and Priamine, shows a high Mw, close to 92 kDa, and narrow molecular weight distribution. This result is interesting, compared to low molecular weights and wide molecular weight distributions obtained during the synthesis of PHUs [53–55], explained with a complex synthesis mechanism that includes numerous side reactions able to create non-reactive chain ends such as ureas, oxazolidinones, and alcohols [56]. Adding IPD in the PHU formulation has a negative effect on the polymerization reaction. Nevertheless, using a IPD:Priamine molar ratio 1:3 (sample RP75I25), the Mw is reduced of only $\approx 20\%$ (Mw close to 71 kDa) and a wide molecular weight distribution is recorded (Mn close to 49 kDa, PDI 1.44). In this case, the yield of reaction does not change significantly from the case of sample RP (94.6% and 95.4% respectively). Instead, further increasing the amount of IPD to IPD:Priamine molar ratio 1:1 (sample RP50I50) or IPD:Priamine molar ratio 3:1 (sample RP25I75) induces a dramatic decrease of the Mw to values lower than 20 kDa. As shown in Table 1, it is to be remarked that increasing the IPD amount to IPD:Priamine molar ratio 1:1 or higher, also induces a very relevant decrease of the yield of reaction, $\approx 70\%$ for the sample RP50I50, $\approx 35\%$ for RP25I75. These data are consistent with NMR analysis, which indicated a reduced reactivity of IPD when used at concentrations above 25%.

3.2 | Thermal Properties, Mechanical Properties, and Wettability of PHUs

DSC traces of synthesized PHUs are reported in Figure 1c. Calorimetric analysis reveal the progressive increase of the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polymer with increasing the relative amount of IPD in the IPD/Priamine mixture. The T_g value (see Table 2) is 14°C for RP. Adding IPD at the IPD:Priamine molar ratio 1:3 induces an increase of the T_g to 20°C (sample RP75I25). Further increasing the relative amount of IPD results in T_g values of 30°C for RP50I50 and 45°C for RP25I75. TGA analysis (Figure 1d) shows that the increasing the amount of Priamine enhances the thermal stability of the synthesized PHUs. For all compositions, the degradation process begins around 300°C and completes at $\approx 500^\circ\text{C}$, with higher residual mass recorded for high relative Priamine content PHUs. In details, the weight loss corresponding to the degradation peak (between 474°C and 486°C) is $\approx 61\%$ for RP25I75 and RP50I50 and it increases to $\approx 69\%$ for RP75I25 and 76% for RP. These results suggest that PHUs

FIGURE 1 | (a) FTIR spectra of RCC/Priamine/IPD based PHUs with a zoom in the 3100–2700 cm⁻¹ area; (b) NMR spectra of RCC/Priamine/IPD-based PHUs. In the schemes, the chemical groups involved in the polymerization for each monomer are highlighted with their assignment on the spectra; (c) DSC traces of RCC/Priamine/IPDA based PHUs; (d) TGA curves of RCC/Priamine/IPDA based PHUs.

TABLE 2 | Glass transition temperature (T_g), tensile properties and water contact angles of PHUs.

Code	T_g (°C)	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Stress at yield (MPa)	Elongation at yield (%)	Stress at break (MPa)	Deformation at break (%)	Water contact angle (°)
RP	14	1.69 ± 0.19	0.24 ± 0.04	78.9 ± 11.5	0.23 ± 0.05	1288 ± 64	90.3 ± 1.0
RP75I25	20	9.48 ± 1.70	1.42 ± 0.40	52.9 ± 6.8	3.33 ± 0.50	875 ± 49	89.4 ± 0.9
RP50I50	30	53.9 ± 16.7	4.72 ± 0.49	18.3 ± 3.6	6.30 ± 0.71	240 ± 41	83.0 ± 1.3
RP25I75	45	*	*	*	*	*	*

*Too brittle to obtain a film by compression moulding.

with higher Priamine contents show improved thermal stability, possibly as a consequence of their higher molecular weights [57].

By resuming, all the above findings indicated that RCC is a suitable monomer for the synthesis of fully biobased PHUs. RCC-based PHUs can be successfully polymerized in mass, without any solvent or catalyst, using a highly flexible fatty acid derived diamine (Priamine 1075) or using a mixture of Priamine and a cyclic diamine (IPD) with Priamine:IPD molar ratio ≥ 3 to prevent a drastic drop of the polymerization yield and molecular weight of the obtained polymer. Moreover, the addition of IPD as a co-reactant amine component is able to induce a slight increase of the T_g value of the synthesized PHU in comparison with the PHU obtained by reaction of RCC with a fatty acid derived diamine.

Since their thermoplastic nature, PHU samples were then processed by compression moulding using a hot platen press to produce films with thickness ≈ 100 μm . Only RP, RP75I25 and RP50I50 films were obtained, as RP25I75 resulted too brittle and fragmented during the removal from the mold.

Mechanical properties of RP, RP75I25, and RP50I50 in terms of Young's modulus (MPa), stress at yield (MPa), elongation at yield (%), stress at break (MPa), and deformation at break (%) are reported in Table 2. Tests were performed at 25°C to evaluate the properties in standard conditions, despite thermal analysis results indicate that at this temperature RP and RP75I25 are above their T_g , while RP50I50 is below its T_g .

Representative stress–strain curves are shown in Figure 2a. The RP PHU shows very high ductility, with deformation at break $>1000\%$, and very low Young's modulus. As shown in Table 2, by replacing part of Priamine with the less flexible IPD, a progressive increase of the modulus is induced, despite the stress at yield and the stress at the break of the polymers containing IPD is reduced, as well as the deformation at break. The observed increase in T_g can be attributed to the incorporation of a small, cyclic molecule into the polymer backbone, IPD enhances the elastic modulus and, consequently, the stiffness and brittleness of the material. On the other hand, Priamine, with its long aliphatic chain, contributes to greater ductility and tensile strength. The combination of these two structurally contrasting diamines underpins our strategy to achieve an optimal balance of mechanical properties in the synthesized PHUs.

Rheological characterization of the film-forming composition, i.e. RP, RP75I25, and RP50I50, was carried out. IPD, Priamine, and RCC were preliminarily mixed at room temperature according to their respective ratios used to obtain the PHUs described above. The mixtures were then characterized by monitoring their viscoelastic behavior as a function of temperature, i.e. during the temperature-induced polymerization process. As shown in Figure 2b, all mixtures exhibited comparable behavior, characterized by a progressive decrease in storage and loss moduli as well as viscosity with increasing temperature. A distinct change of the slope of G' associated with PHU polymerization, was observed, centered at around 72°C for RP50I50, and $\approx 90^\circ\text{C}$ for RP75I25 and RP. This behavior indicates that increasing the IPD content shifts the polymerization toward lower temperatures, whereas higher Priamine contents (75% and 100%) promote polymerization at higher temperatures. The absence of a crossover between the

storage and loss moduli in RP50I50 and RP suggests that these systems remain predominantly viscous throughout the entire temperature range. In contrast, the moduli of RP75I25 nearly overlap after polymerization, revealing a slightly higher elastic contribution and, consequently, an increased stiffness. In Figure S2 the isotherms performed on the samples revealed the absence of any transition at low deformation, consistent with a typical thermoplastic behavior.

Equilibrium water content tests (Figure 2c) showed a behavior in agreement with WCA tests: The amount of absorbed water after 1, 2, or 7 days of water immersion showed the trend RP50I50 (EWC 11.2 wt.% at 7 days) $>$ RP75I25 (EWC 10.9 wt.% at 7 days) $>$ RP (EWC 10.4 wt.% at 7 days) confirming the low affinity of all the samples toward water, with only a slightly increased water affinity of the samples containing higher amounts of IPD hardener. As concerning gel content tests, after soaking in water even for 7 days, the amount of extracted polymer was in all cases not appreciable, indicating the good water resistance of the samples.

As concerning their wettability, (Figure 2d and Table 2), according to swelling tests showed in Figure 2c, all samples show a partially hydrophobic behavior, with WCA close to 90°; the formulation containing the highest amount of IPD (sample RP50I50) shows an improved hydrophilicity, with the WCA lowered to $\approx 83^\circ$.

3.3 | Adhesive Properties of PHUs

RP and RP75I25 were selected to perform adhesive tests. For this application RP50I50 was discarded due to its pronounced brittleness, evidenced by tensile tests. First, DMA was performed on RP and RP75I25 to evaluate their applicability range as adhesive layers. Results shown in Figure 3a, related to RP75I25, revealed that as the temperature increases, G' is higher than G'' up to 21°C. Beyond this point, the two moduli overlap up to $\approx 61^\circ\text{C}$. This behavior indicates that, below 21°C, the material exhibits predominantly elastic behavior, as $G' > G''$, meaning that the polymer chains are relatively rigid and energy is mostly stored elastically during deformation. In this same temperature range, the viscosity increases up to 21°C and then remains approximately constant, with $\tan \delta$ close to 1. This trend is consistent with the evolution of the viscoelastic moduli. Between 21°C and 61°C, the overlap of G' and G'' , began approximately at 100 MPa, suggests a transition region, likely associated with the T_g . In this range, the polymer shows both elastic and viscous characteristics, with comparable energy storage and dissipation and both moduli decrease by roughly two orders of magnitude. At 61°C viscoelastic properties collapsed and the polymer became extremely rubbery. Therefore, below 21°C, the material behaves as a rigid, glassy solid, which limits its ability to wet the substrate and reduces tack. In the 21°C–61°C range, G' and G'' are comparable ($\tan \delta \approx 1$) and progressively decrease by about two orders of magnitude, indicating a balanced viscoelastic response that favors both wetting and cohesive strength, a key requirement for effective adhesion. Above 61°C, both moduli drop, suggesting a transition to a soft or rubber-like state where cohesive strength decreases, thus reducing adhesive performance. Qualitatively, RP behavior (Figure 3b) is quite similar to RP75I25 one, with different temperature working ranges. Indeed, RP appears rigid until 12°C, while G' and G'' became comparable (also in this case around

FIGURE 2 | (a) Representative stress strain curves of RP, RP75I25 and RP50I50 films; b) storage and loss modulus and viscosity (G' , G'' and $|\eta^*|$) of RP50I50, RP75I25 and RP; (c) equilibrium water content (EWC) of the samples after 1, 2, and 7 days of water immersion; (d) water contact angles (WCA) images of RP, RP75I25 and RP50I50 films.

100 MPa, and consequently $\tan \delta \approx 1$) until $\approx 44^\circ\text{C}$, at which the moduli decrease to 1 MPa, and too soft after this temperature. This means that the optimal adhesive performance for RP are comprehended in the 12–44°C range, which is slightly thinner and translated to lower temperatures with respect to RP75I25.

As detailed in the experimental, RP and RP75I25 layers were applied on aluminum, CFRP and wood substrates and treated

at 150°C to prepare adhesive joints. These processing conditions were deliberately selected outside the applicability range identified from the DMA in order to homogenize the systems and make it independent of the intrinsic differences arising from the use of different materials, both as adhesives and as joints. The adhesive properties of the selected PHUs on aluminum, CFRP and wood joints were evaluated by lap shear test. Figure 3c shows a schematic representation of the single lap joints (SLJ)

FIGURE 3 | (a) DMA curves of RP75I25; (b) DMA curves of RP; (c) geometry (mm) of single-lap joints tested; (d) representative shear stress–strain curves obtained by lap-shear tests of RP and RP75I25 an aluminium joints; (e) representative shear stress–strain curves obtained by lap-shear tests of RP and RP75I25 an CFRP joints; (f) representative shear stress–strain curves obtained by lap-shear tests of RP and RP75I25 a wood joints.

prepared. As shown in Figure 3d, the lap shear tests carried out on the aluminum joint prepared with RP adhesive layer showed a maximum shear stress of ≈ 2.21 MPa at a deformation of ≈ 1.5 mm, where the failure of the adhesive occurred. The maximum load shown by the RP75I25 adhesive was very significantly improved, with a maximum shear stress of more than 3.93 MPa recorded at 1.7 mm deformation. Lower shear stress capacity of the adhesives were observed for CFRP joints (Figure 3e), but the behavior was similar to that recorded for aluminum. RP showed a lower adhesive capacity (≈ 0.27 MPa at 0.7 mm of deformation) whereas a significant improvement was recorded for the RP75I25 adhesive, with a maximum shear stress of ≈ 1.52 MPa at 0.45 mm of deformation. Regarding the adhesive performance of PHUs on wood joints (Figure 3f), the RP and RP75I25 adhesives show a similar trend to the previous cases: RP75I25 exhibits a higher shear stress, reaching 3.26 MPa at 1.8 mm of deformation, while RP achieves 0.80 MPa at 0.6 mm. Overall, the adhesive performance of PHUs on wood appears superior to that on CFRP and slightly lower than that on aluminum. Table S1 presents a comparison of commercial polyurethane and RP75I25 adhesives in terms of their mechanical and thermal properties, as well as their applicability to different substrates. The Table highlights the high versatility of RP75I25, which can be applied to various types of substrates and exhibits mechanical performance and thermal applicability slightly lower than those of commercial analogues. Nevertheless, it retains a thermoplastic nature that ensures easy processability, allowing the adhesive layer to be reprocessed or even removed through simple thermal treatment, which is a feature not possible for crosslinked commercial polymers. To be noticed is that the adhesive performances of RP75I25 are in the same range of those reported

in the literature for joints bonded with conventional epoxy adhesives [58–60].

To better explain the results obtained by using the mixture of Priamine/IPD in the RP75I25 adhesive layer, the morphology of the failure surfaces of the SLJ plates after lap shear tests was investigated by optical microscopy and SEM (Figure 4).

Each sample reveals the good adhesive properties of RP and RP75I25 on the tested samples. In details, Figure 4a,c,e shows the optical images and SEM image of one plate of an aluminum, CFRP and wood, respectively, SLJ realized with the RP adhesive. As shown, fragmented adhesive residues are found on the adherend plate (Figure 4a1), and this is confirmed by the SEM image (Figure 4a2), indicating a cohesive failure mechanism, typical of a good interaction between the adhesive and the substrate, for which the adhesive failure occurs within the adhesive layer. The same cohesive failure mechanism is found also for CFRP and wood, as shown in Figure 4c1,e1, respectively, and confirmed by SEM images shown in Figure 4c2,e2, respectively.

The cohesive mechanism is confirmed for the RP75I25 adhesive, as shown in Figure 4b,d,f for aluminum, CFRP and wood, respectively. Indeed, adhesive residues are evidenced on both plates of the aluminum (Figure 4b1,b2), CFRP (Figure 4d1,d2) and wood (Figure 4f1,f2) SLJ and SEM micrographs on the two plates after the test (Figure 4b3,4,b5,6 for aluminum, d3,4 and d5,6 for CFRP and f3,4 and f5,6 for wood, respectively) well show adhesive residues on both plates. Thus the improved adhesive performances of RP75I25 on aluminum in comparison to RP is not due to a different failure mechanism of the adhesives, but mainly

FIGURE 4 | Optical microscopy and SEM images of plates after lap shear tests on single lap joints: (a) aluminium plates with RP adhesive; (b) aluminium plates with RP75I25 adhesive; (c) CFRP plates with RP adhesive; (d) CFRP plates with RP75I25 adhesive; (e) wood plates with RP adhesive; (f) wood plates with RP75I25 adhesive.

to the improved mechanical property of the polymer containing in the formulation the rigid IPD replacing part of the flexible, fatty acid derived diamine.

Thus, the strong adhesion of the selected PHU in substantially independent from the choice of the substrate, since the high difference between aluminum, CFRP and wood, revealing as a very promising versatile bio-based adhesive.

4 | Conclusions

The solvent- and catalyst-free synthesis of poly(hydroxyurethane)s (PHUs) was successfully carried out via polyaddition between resorcinol bis(cyclocarbonate) (RCC) and IPD/Priamine mixtures at molar ratios of 0:1, 1:3, 1:1, and 3:1. The chemical, thermal, and mechanical properties of the resulting PHUs were thoroughly investigated. The incorporation of small amounts of IPD relative to Priamine led to the formation of promising biobased polymers. Notably, increasing the IPD content resulted in a significant reduction in reaction yield, and PHU films containing 50 mol% IPD of the total amine content were found to be too brittle for practical use. This brittleness was effectively mitigated by limiting the IPD content to 25 mol% of the total amines. The two most promising formulations (with IPD/Priamine 1:3 and 0:1 molar ratio), which were found to be pure enough not to require purification, owing to their high synthesis yield, were further evaluated as adhesive layers for metal and composite substrates. Among them, the PHU containing 25 mol% IPD exhibited the best adhesive performance, comparable to that of commercial epoxy resins, with a maximum load of ≈ 390 N at 0.45 mm of deformation. These results demonstrate that PHUs synthesized through sustainable, solvent-catalyst- and isocyanate-free processes using biobased monomers hold significant potential for advanced applications. By carefully tuning their composition, it is possible to adjust rigidity without compromising flexibility and processability, yielding materials with performance comparable to fossil-based counterparts.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File: mame70154-sup-0001-SuppMat.pdf